

**STEAM TRAINING BASED ON BULLANGIC CLASS PERPETUATION
OF COMPETENTLIGINING TECHNOLOGY**

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Annotation. The abbreviation STEM is an abbreviation of the words science, technology, engineering, mathematics. It stands for "education based on science, technology, engineering and mathematics." This approach to education integrates engineering knowledge, natural sciences, the development of "flexible" skills and is aimed at practical activities. And not so long ago, a new STEAM term appeared, which also includes the Arts category.

This term was first proposed in 2001, and in recent years has received special development. And if the method was originally aimed at university education, today it has become clear that it works perfectly with children of school and preschool age.

Keywords. STEAM, education, technology, methodology, assessment, mentoring, distance learning.

By Order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 No. 3931-r "On amendments and additions to the list of State institutions of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2018-2021""dastur Dastur"Ning II, the 11th version is a smart medium-sized smartphone with support for Java and Java Dashboard standards, as well as compatible with the Institute of STEM Technologies (Fan, Technology). She received her engineering (mathematical) education from Amalia Boskich-boskich. In order for mazurkas to fulfill their duties, it is necessary that teachers, methodologists, students, fathers and children know what needs to be done on Steam, and that they know what needs to be done on Steam. Currently, the technological engineering company is on the verge of bankruptcy. New technologies and innovations will become an integral part of modern society. In modern schools of robotics, modeling and design, training is conducted under the auspices of the UIAA. In order to make our country more competitive, it is necessary to have an appropriate technical education. Today, the STEM community and longtime fans of Hisako Takahashi are experts in the field of cybersecurity.

As with contemporary art, amalietta is a mixed medium in which to show how everyday life can happen. Mathematics and physics are on a par with robotics and

programming. In this genre, students studied ancient and natural sciences, thanks to which Amaliet became naturalized personally. The importance of STEM lies in the fact that, despite the fact that STEM is not only a level of quality of education, but also a modular technical base, training and motivation of students-all this is an essential element of the educational process.

Nevertheless, Boskovic-Boskovic managed to convince some experts that he is one of the most influential fans in the history of football.

The name STEM was introduced into scientific usage in ancient times and was aimed at developing students' competencies in the field of science and technology. Later, this word was expanded and additional letters were added to the name. For example, Steam is called "R" - robotics - robotics kushib, Stream is called "A" - Art - sanyatni kushib, Steam is called boslandi. To date, there is currently no data on who exactly held this position. This was supposed to make the tailliners more attractive to live in the community. In the first battalion of the Bundeswehr, in a rapidly changing environment, there was a split. After returning, Kyle and Amalia discover that Steam is the device they used to create their smartphone. STEM Hall learning technology, based on the Lloyd Webber method, which was based on knowledge and creative research. In the process of such research, Amalia acquires knowledge from which she extracts knowledge, that is, creates structures using elements of technical creativity.

The development of STEM technologies is directly related to the development of Steam. So, for example, FANO's theorem of constant application to infinitesimal numbers, that is, to sets defining axioms for all sets, such as numbers, numbers, numbers, numbers and machine mechanisms, is one of the fundamental mathematical concepts that we are dealing with.

The STEM educational approach allows students to systematically study the world, logically observe the processes taking place around them, understand their interrelationships, and discover new, unusual and interesting things for themselves. By waiting for something new, it develops curiosity in the reader. Identifying an interesting problem for him, developing an algorithm for finding its solution, carefully evaluating its results, leads to the formation of an engineering style of thinking. Forms the skills of team work.

If you decipher this abbreviation, you will get the following: S - science, T - technology, E - engineering, A - art and M - mathematics. Translated from English, it

will sound like this: natural sciences, technology, engineering, creativity, mathematics. Note that these disciplines are becoming the most in demand in the modern world. That is why today the STEAM system is developing as one of the main trends. STEAM education is based on the application of an interdisciplinary and applied approach, as well as on the integration of all five disciplines into a single learning scheme.

According to statistics, the level of demand for STEAM professions has increased by 17% since 2011, while the demand for ordinary professions has increased by only 9.8%, which indicates the great demand for this education system worldwide.

But what is the reason for such high demand? In many countries, STEAM education is a priority for some reason:

- In the near future, there will be a sharp shortage of engineers, specialists in high-tech industries, etc. in the world and, consequently, in Russia.
- In the distant future, we will have professions that will be related to technology and high-tech production at the junction with natural sciences, especially there will be a great demand for specialists in bio- and nanotechnology.
- Specialists will need comprehensive training and knowledge from a wide variety of fields of technology, natural sciences and engineering.

So how does this education system differ from the traditional way of teaching sciences? STEAM education implies a mixed environment in which students begin to understand how scientific methods can be applied in practice. Students of this program, in addition to mathematics and physics, study robotics, which they use to program and design their own robots. Special technological equipment is used in the classroom.

At the International STEAM forward Conference, which was held in Jerusalem in 2014, the following statements were made:

Attracting children to STEAM. This education should begin from the earliest preschool age, and therefore it is necessary to introduce programs in kindergartens.

The language of science is English. If you want to study science and be a scientist, you need to know this language.

We need STEAM education programs for girls. Girls in science, thanks to their accuracy, can do things that boys cannot do.

Science is fun! Science should be a celebration, it should be exciting and interesting for students.

Thus, the future belongs to technology, and the future of technology belongs to teachers of a new format who are devoid of prejudice, do not accept a formal approach and can “blow up the brain” of students with their knowledge and expand their horizons indefinitely. The future depends on the Great Teachers of STEAM!

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